

GEOLOGIC MAP, LANDING SITE SELECTION AND TRAVERSE PLANNING IN COPERNICUS CRATER. Riccardo Pozzoboni¹, Filippo Tusberti¹, Maurizio Pajola², Matteo Massironi^{1,3}, ¹Department of Geosciences, University of Padova, Via Gradenigo 6, 35131, Padova (Italy), ²INAF – Padova Astronomic Observatory, Vicolo dell’Osservatorio 5, 35122, Padova (Italy), ³Center of Studies and Activities for Space “G. Colombo”, University of Padova, Via Venezia 15, 35131, Padova (Italy).

Introduction: Copernicus Crater is a relatively young impact crater of ~800 Ma with a diameter of ~100 km and it is located on the lunar near side. Developed within the PlanMap H2020 project, we hereby present two geologic maps, at a broad and local scale, and the technical evaluation as a landing site with possible traverse paths and sampling sites. The scientific rationale guiding this study is that Copernicus is pivotal to refine the lunar time scale and because of its particular composition. Sample returns could provide absolute ages useful to improve both the lunar crater chronology and, by extrapolation, that of other inner solar system terrestrial bodies. Moreover, olivine spectral signature was detected [1], and this can provide information about the lunar crust and mantle. The whole central peak represents, in fact, exhumed deep olivine-rich troctolite [1]. This work is timely given the foreseen human assisted robotic missions proposal and Artemis programs that both can benefit from the outcomes of these analyses.

Data and methods: As base maps for broader scale geologic mapping of the crater we made use of the merged DEM of LOLA+Kaguya at 59 m of grid spacing and LROC WAC 100m/pixel mosaic. This was integrated with spectral observations in order to recognize lithological variations and to better define the geologic units.

To do that, the Clementine UVVIS color ratio mosaic was used: the band ratios combined in an RGB mosaic were used to determine the relative abundance in titanium, olivine and mafic minerals in general, and volcanic glasses.

Higher resolution geologic mapping, landing site and traverse definition analysis were carried out on mosaics of LROC NAC images, with high and low incidence angles scaled at 5 m/pixel. This resolution was chosen as a compromise between the need of high detail for landing and traverse definition and the need of a first screening of a relatively large area. The images with low incidence angles were used, together with the Clementine band ratio mosaic to identify the compositional units, whereas the higher incidence was used to better constrain the morphologies and obstacles.

Mapping and traverse definition: The geologic mapping was at first performed at a broad scale of 1:400.000 both on Clementine, WAC images, and DEM shaded relief in order to detect the broad geologic context in terms of smoothness of terrains, obstacles, general morphologies and potentially

interesting areas in terms of composition. As a second step, to assess the possibility of landing in Copernicus maximizing safety and scientific return we used the LROC NAC mosaic. We mapped in higher detail landforms previously identified at a larger scale, aiming to plan rover traverses and scientific stops (for potential in-situ analysis and/or sampling) as well as to define possible obstacles and hazards. Therefore, a second geologic map at higher resolution (1:100.000) of NW quadrant of Copernicus was produced. We selected this location for its relatively high smoothness, low number of obstacles and significant hazards. Three different landing ellipses were selected: sizes were derived from the NASA Mars rovers MSL Curiosity and Mars2020, since to date no constraints are available for the Moon and their location was chosen in order to avoid obstacles and to be as meaningful as possible in terms of sites of interest in the surroundings.

Hazards related to rock abundance were investigated within the landing ellipses according to [2] as well as for small impact craters together with overall surface slope. Following the constraints defined for Schrödinger crater exploration in the HERACLES program [3] six traverses were defined: three long and three short traverses, of 32 and 16 km respectively. The sampling sites/stops within all the foreseen traverses (from a minimum of 13 to a maximum of 19 per traverse with a variable time duration from 6 to 18 days [3]) were chosen to maximise the scientific return, following the future science goals in in situ lunar exploration [4].

b

Figure 1: in a) the geomorphologic mapping of Copernicus crater at a scale of 1:400.000 overlaid in transparency on LOLA-Kaguya shaded relief DEM. For the units description we forward to the PlanMap data repository https://data.planmap.eu/pub/moon/PM-MOO-MS-Copernicus_01/. In white it is marked the area of higher resolution mapping at 1:100.000 shown in b). Here more landforms were characterized and proposed rover traverses are visible in red, cyan and pink. The dashed lines identify the short traverses.

Conclusions: This work represent a first assessment for landing on the near side of the Moon in a well-known location that would provide insights in the lunar crust composition and evolution as well as new constraints to the lunar chronology. This investigation could provide a baseline for future and more detailed analyses as soon as more engineering and scientific constraints will be provided for unmanned or manned landings on the lunar near side both from the Heracles and Artemis programs aiming to return to the moon in this decade.

This research was supported by European Union's Horizon 2020 under grant agreement No 776276-PLANMAP.

References: [1] Liu, F., Yang, R., Zhang, Y., Qiao, L., Wang, S., Yang, Y., & Wang, X. (2011). Distribution of olivine and pyroxene derived from Clementine data in Crater Copernicus. *Journal of Earth Science*, 22(5), 586–594. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12583-011-0209-2>

[2] Pajola, M., Rossato, S., Baratti, E., Pozzobon, R., Quantin, C., Carter, J., & Thollot, P. (2017). Boulder abundances and size-frequency distributions

on Oxia Planum-Mars: Scientific implications for the 2020 ESA ExoMars rover. *Icarus*, 296(May 2017), 1339–1351.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icarus.2017.05.011>

[3] Steenstra, E., Martin, D., McDonald, F., Paisarnsombat, S., Venturino, C., O'Hara, S., ... Kring, D. A. (2016). Analyses of Robotic Traverses and Sample Sites in the Schrödinger basin for the HERACLES Human-Assisted Sample Return Mission Concept. In *Advances in Space Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2016.05.041>

[4] Massironi, M., & Ferrari, S. (2019). Future science goals of in situ Lunar explorations. *International Workshop on Metrology for AeroSpace*.